

THE ISSUE OF THE THRONE OF THE AFRIGHIDS IN KHOREZM (AS AN EXAMPLE OF NUMISMATIC RESEARCH)

Rajapov Mardonbek Qosimboy o`g`li

PhD student at the History Institute of the Academy of Sciences. Telefon: +998914299977

Elektron pochta: mardonbekoff@gmail.com.

In terms of its rich history, material and spiritual culture, Old Khorezm occupies a worthy place not only in the historical development of Central Asia, but also in the world. The history of Khorezm in the early Middle Ages is one of the most understudied archeologically relevant topics, as well as the lack of written sources is standing. Taking into account the scarcity of written sources, it would be appropriate to study the early medieval history of Khorezm through archeological and numismatic sources, as well as to reconsider the opinions expressed about the history of the Afrighid dynasty of Khorezm.

Beruni provided information about the coming to the throne of the Afrighid dynasty and the first ruler of this dynasty. It is traditionally believed that this event occurred in 304-305 AD. However, a new approach to the date of this year has emerged based on numismatic materials. According to Beruni's information, it is related to building Al-Fir Palace. If we analyze these data, the construction of the palace corresponds to 304-305 AD. It is possible that the beginning date of the dynasty started even earlier. The first king of the dynasty was Wazamar (Afrig`). Wazamar is the name of a king, and Afrig is the name of a dynasty. Therefore, it is proposed to call the name of the dynasty Wazamarids (Afrighids). The rulers of this dynasty ruled for 600 years until the Ma'munid dynasty. At the end of the III century AD, Khorezm established its own regular minting of silver and copper coins. And it is most likely that Khorezm will come out of the crisis and become a new powerful state, a new state that can ensure the regular minting of coins. It was a sign that it would happen. At the same time, when numismatic materials provide real information about the list of Khorezm rulers, Beruni's semi-legendary information shows that the name Afrig is absent from Khorezm coins of the end of the III - beginning of the IV century, according to S. P. Tolstov, the name Afrig ('pryk) is found in the inscription of the rarest Khorezm coin ". A similar coin was published by B.I. Weinberg in the collection at the State Hermitage. But according to V. A. Livshits, in the inscription of this coin. The name "Bivarsar" (bwrsr) The same name appears on a coin published by S. P. Tolstov. According to Beruni, the reign of Afrig dates back to 304-305 AD, and according to stratigraphic data, it bears the name of King Wazamara minted at Khorezm. completely corresponds to the date of the silver coins. This date is assigned by B. I. Weinberg to the last quarter of the III - the beginning of the IV century. Its existence is not a coincidence, it is a historical fact with sources. The rulers of this dynasty used the same ancient Aramaic title (MLK' - king). However, the naming and writing of the title changed over time. That

is, the titles were written first, then the name of the king. Such changes do not mean a change of dynasty, because the dynasty symbol remains the same. This order of placing the titles and names of the ruling kings in the legends is typical of the legends on the coins of the ancient states - Greco-Bactria and Kushan. The traditional translation of the titles “MR'Y”, “MLK” is "Mister King", but it does not exclude the fact that it reflects the concept of "king of kings". This Aramaic title was put on coins until the reign of the last non-Muslim kings of Khorezm - Saushafan and Azkatsvar II (mid-eighth century AD - second half). At the same time, from the 8th century onwards, in Arabic sources

Another name was used for the kings of Khorezm - Khorezmshah, for example, Khorezmshah Chagan. Perhaps the title "king" - "Khorazmshah" appeared relatively late in Khorezm - as a result of certain contacts with Sassanid Iran in the 3rd century and was used together with Aramaic titles at that time. Beruni's data and numismatic data serve as the main source for the sequence and chronology of the reign of Khorezm kings from the Wazamarids (Afrighids) dynasty. The names of the kings are more accurately conveyed by Beruni in the inscriptions on coins written in the ancient Khorezm script than in their Arabic rendering. Basically, the names of the Beruni kings and the names of the kings on the coins of Khorezm with the rarest exceptions, do not correspond to each other. In addition, Beruni does not give the chronology of the reign of the Khorezm kings, thanks to the analysis of iconographic features and archeological-stratigraphic data, B. I. Weinberg was able to more accurately determine the chronological framework of the reign of the Khorezm kings. Beruni mentions the names of 22 rulers of Khorezm. The following situation also attracts attention: the list of B. I. Weinberg and V. A. Livshits shows the names of 13 Khorezmshahs who sat on the throne from the first half of the IV century to the end of the VIII century, that is, until the reign of the Muslim Afrighids. In the list of M. N. Fedorov and A. Kuznetsov there are 19 names in the same chronological order. In Beruni, 16 Afrighid rulers are mentioned in the same period. This period lasts about 500 years, from the first half of the IV century to the end of the VIII century. In general, the names of the Khorezm rulers and the sequence of their reigns determined by V. A. Livshits and B. I. Weinberg remain the closest to the truth. However, we believe that the first king of this dynasty was Wazamar (Afrig), and the next one was Biwarsar (dywrsr), according to Beruni, Biwarsar was probably Bogra.

Another information about Khorezm political administration system is the existence of titles "Khisrav" and "Baghpur". The title "Khisrav" appears for the first time in the work of the Arab author Ba`lami as the ruler of the region called Hamjerd. According to S.P. Tolstov, the above two titles were used at the same time. Khisrav-Khorazmshah was a ruler in religious affairs, "Baghpur" was a ruler in secular affairs. But the numismatist B. I. Weinberg rejects both of the above opinions and states that these two titles were applied to the same ruler at the same time.

A number of documents in Khorezm script and language found in the Tupraqqala contain information about the administrative management system in effect in Khorezm. Among the palace officials, "prmt`r" is the chief economist. The title of "farmondor [commander]" is mentioned in

the documents. This title and position is also found in Sughd and Iranian Sassanids, inherited from the Achaemenid era and later. The holder of this title is the prime minister and has solved economic issues throughout the country. The term "srk`r" is found in a document written on a spool clay tablet found in the Tuprakqla. In some documents, the additions "srkr'n"- "sarkaron" and "srkr"- "sarkora" are also mentioned. The task of this position is to lead certain areas, that is, it is considered a leader. The sarkars ruled the craft villages or neighborhoods. They were also responsible for the quality and quantity of products coming to the palace.

In conclusion, on the basis of new information, the chronology and history of the Wasamarid (Afrighid) dynasty is presented. Unfortunately, there is little information about the internal history of the Afrighids before the Muslim Afrighids. Accordingly about the state they created due to the lack of written sources. Above the mentioned the history of the Afrighids dynasty with rare exceptions, mainly represented by numismatic data and Beruni's recent data.

List of references

1. Abu Rahyon Beruniy. Tanlangan asarlar, 1-jild. Toshkent.1968.
2. Bosworth, Clifford Edmund (1984a). "Āl-e Afīg̃". Encyclopaedia Iranica, Vol. I, Fasc. 7. pp. 743–745.
3. Бирюков Д.В. Нумизматика Центральной Азии. Исследования и гипотезы. Ташкент, 2010.
4. Вайнберг.Б.И. Монеты древнего Хорезма. М.:Наука,1977.
5. Гулямов Я.Г. История орошения Хорезма с древнейших времен до наших дней. – Т.: Фан, 1957
6. Мамбетуллаев М.М, Манылов Ю.П. Городище Топрак-кала крепности сооружение.- ОНУ. -Т.: Фан, 1997, №3
7. Мамбетуллаев М.М., Юсупов Н. Археологические работы в Хорезмской обдасти в 1973 году //АО-1973.-М.: Наука, 1974
8. Ртвеладзе Э.В. История и нумизматика Чача. Ташкент. 2006
9. Толстов С.П. Древний Хорезм.-М.,1948
10. Хорезм в истории государственности Узбекистана. – Ташкент: «Ўзбекистон файласу флари миллий жамияти», 2013.